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GLM Tf2 EG CpG1 AY1 Est BY YEAR_ MONTH_
/METHOD=SSTYPE(3)
/INTERCEPT=INCLUDE
/POSTHOC=YEAR_ MONTH_(LSD)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(OVERALL)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(YEAR_)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(MONTH_)
/EMMEANS=TABLES(YEAR_*MONTH_)
/PRINT=DESCRIPTIVE ETASQ OPOWER HOMOGENEITY
/CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05)
/DESIGN= YEAR_ MONTH_ YEAR_*MONTH_ .

```

General Linear Model

Notes

Output Created	20-JUL-2021 17:09:50	
Comments		
Input	Data	/Users/sureshnair/Desktop/Restriction_Assay/data file.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	12
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the model.

Notes

Syntax		GLM Tf2 EG CpG1 AY1 Est BY YEAR_ MONTH_ /METHOD=SSTYPE(3) /INTERCEPT=INCLUDE /POSTHOC=YEAR_ MONTH_(LSD) /EMMEANS=TABLES (OVERALL) /EMMEANS=TABLES (YEAR_) /EMMEANS=TABLES (MONTH_) /EMMEANS=TABLES (YEAR_*MONTH_) /PRINT=DESCRIPTIVE ETASQ OPOWER HOMOGENEITY /CRITERIA=ALPHA(.05) /DESIGN= YEAR_ MONTH_ YEAR_*MONTH_.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.00

Warnings

Box's Test of Equality of Covariance Matrices is not computed because there are fewer than two nonsingular cell covariance matrices.
Post hoc tests are not performed for YEAR, not periodic because there are fewer than three groups.

Between-Subjects Factors

		N
YEAR, not periodic	2017	6
	2018	6
MONTH, period 12	6	4
	8	4
	11	4

Descriptive Statistics

	YEAR, not periodic	MONTH, period 12	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Transposon	2017	6	4.150	2.8991	2
		8	9.650	1.6263	2
		11	2.500	.0000	2
		Total	5.433	3.6637	6
	2018	6	6.600	.9899	2
		8	10.350	3.8891	2
		11	28.600	.2828	2
		Total	15.183	10.6796	6
	Total	6	5.375	2.2648	4
		8	10.000	2.4671	4
		11	15.550	15.0697	4
		Total	10.308	9.1581	12
Endoglucanase	2017	6	40.065	9.5247	2
		8	20.900	6.5054	2
		11	16.150	1.6263	2
		Total	25.705	12.4650	6
	2018	6	47.910	10.1965	2
		8	54.055	6.8519	2
		11	28.900	23.3345	2
		Total	43.622	16.6335	6
	Total	6	43.988	9.2418	4
		8	37.478	19.9041	4
		11	22.525	15.3808	4
		Total	34.663	16.8503	12
CYP6ER1	2017	6	22.320	4.4972	2
		8	39.195	4.8154	2
		11	36.700	1.8385	2
		Total	32.738	8.7022	6
	2018	6	31.950	9.1217	2
		8	34.800	1.1314	2
		11	42.100	4.6669	2
		Total	36.283	6.5710	6
	Total	6	27.135	8.0863	4
		8	36.998	3.8203	4
		11	39.400	4.2552	4
		Total	34.511	7.5813	12
CYP6AY1	2017	6	22.6000	7.35391	2
		8	40.3100	.57983	2
		11	40.7000	6.64680	2
		Total	34.5367	10.25866	6
	2018	6	21.2900	.00000	2
		8	31.6900	9.80050	2

Descriptive Statistics

YEAR, not periodic		MONTH, period 12	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
		11	14.8200	.46669	2
		Total	22.6000	8.78650	6
Total		6	21.9450	4.31262	4
		8	36.0000	7.54300	4
		11	27.7600	15.42911	4
		Total	28.5683	11.03575	12
Carboxyesterase	2017	6	22.030	14.3260	2
		8	27.000	1.6971	2
		11	2.695	2.1284	2
		Total	17.242	13.2073	6
	2018	6	42.620	10.2955	2
		8	33.400	10.4652	2
		11	30.800	21.3546	2
		Total	35.607	12.8519	6
	Total	6	32.325	15.6544	4
		8	30.200	7.1498	4
		11	16.748	20.4160	4
		Total	26.424	15.6955	12

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.999	743.803 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.001	743.803 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Hotelling's Trace	1859.507	743.803 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Roy's Largest Root	1859.507	743.803 ^b	5.000	2.000
YEAR_	Pillai's Trace	.948	7.293 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.052	7.293 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Hotelling's Trace	18.232	7.293 ^b	5.000	2.000
	Roy's Largest Root	18.232	7.293 ^b	5.000	2.000
MONTH_	Pillai's Trace	1.852	7.535	10.000	6.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.005	5.295 ^b	10.000	4.000
	Hotelling's Trace	27.906	2.791	10.000	2.000
	Roy's Largest Root	18.520	11.112 ^c	5.000	3.000
YEAR_ * MONTH_	Pillai's Trace	1.786	5.010	10.000	6.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.008	4.012 ^b	10.000	4.000
	Hotelling's Trace	24.030	2.403	10.000	2.000
	Roy's Largest Root	18.922	11.353 ^c	5.000	3.000

Multivariate Tests^a

Effect		Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^d
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.001	.999	3719.015	1.000
	Wilks' Lambda	.001	.999	3719.015	1.000
	Hotelling's Trace	.001	.999	3719.015	1.000
	Roy's Largest Root	.001	.999	3719.015	1.000
YEAR_	Pillai's Trace	.125	.948	36.463	.344
	Wilks' Lambda	.125	.948	36.463	.344
	Hotelling's Trace	.125	.948	36.463	.344
	Roy's Largest Root	.125	.948	36.463	.344
MONTH_	Pillai's Trace	.011	.926	75.350	.928
	Wilks' Lambda	.061	.930	52.955	.607
	Hotelling's Trace	.293	.933	27.906	.176
	Roy's Largest Root	.038	.949	55.560	.722
YEAR_ * MONTH_	Pillai's Trace	.031	.893	50.097	.784
	Wilks' Lambda	.096	.909	40.124	.489
	Hotelling's Trace	.329	.923	24.030	.160
	Roy's Largest Root	.036	.950	56.766	.730

a. Design: Intercept + YEAR_ + MONTH_ + YEAR_ * MONTH_

b. Exact statistic

c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.

d. Computed using alpha =

Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances^a

	F	df1	df2	Sig.
Transposon	.	5	6	.
Endoglucanase	.	5	6	.
CYP6ER1	.	5	6	.
CYP6AY1	.	5	6	.
Carboxyesterase	.	5	6	.

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Design: Intercept + YEAR_ + MONTH_ + YEAR_ * MONTH_

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Corrected Model	Transposon	895.334 ^a	5	179.067	39.449
	Endoglucanase	2292.156 ^b	5	458.431	3.310
	CYP6ER1	479.174 ^c	5	95.835	3.757
	CYP6AY1	1144.801 ^d	5	228.960	7.050
	Carboxyesterase	1825.658 ^e	5	365.132	2.478
Intercept	Transposon	1275.141	1	1275.141	280.920
	Endoglucanase	14418.560	1	14418.560	104.092
	CYP6ER1	14291.971	1	14291.971	560.258
	CYP6AY1	9793.796	1	9793.796	301.558
	Carboxyesterase	8378.839	1	8378.839	56.858
YEAR_	Transposon	285.188	1	285.188	62.828
	Endoglucanase	963.021	1	963.021	6.952
	CYP6ER1	37.701	1	37.701	1.478
	CYP6AY1	427.452	1	427.452	13.162
	Carboxyesterase	1011.820	1	1011.820	6.866
MONTH_	Transposon	207.632	2	103.816	22.871
	Endoglucanase	968.795	2	484.398	3.497
	CYP6ER1	337.962	2	168.981	6.624
	CYP6AY1	399.006	2	199.503	6.143
	Carboxyesterase	570.859	2	285.429	1.937
YEAR_ * MONTH_	Transposon	402.515	2	201.257	44.338
	Endoglucanase	360.340	2	180.170	1.301
	CYP6ER1	103.512	2	51.756	2.029
	CYP6AY1	318.343	2	159.171	4.901
	Carboxyesterase	242.979	2	121.490	.824
Error	Transposon	27.235	6	4.539	
	Endoglucanase	831.102	6	138.517	
	CYP6ER1	153.058	6	25.510	
	CYP6AY1	194.864	6	32.477	
	Carboxyesterase	884.181	6	147.363	
Total	Transposon	2197.710	12		
	Endoglucanase	17541.817	12		
	CYP6ER1	14924.204	12		
	CYP6AY1	11133.461	12		
	Carboxyesterase	11088.677	12		
Corrected Total	Transposon	922.569	11		
	Endoglucanase	3123.257	11		
	CYP6ER1	632.232	11		
	CYP6AY1	1339.665	11		
	Carboxyesterase	2709.838	11		

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Noncent. Parameter	Observed Power ^f
Corrected Model	Transposon	.000	.970	197.246	1.000
	Endoglucanase	.089	.734	16.548	.523
	CYP6ER1	.069	.758	18.784	.581
	CYP6AY1	.017	.855	35.249	.859
	Carboxyesterase	.150	.674	12.389	.406
Intercept	Transposon	.000	.979	280.920	1.000
	Endoglucanase	.000	.946	104.092	1.000
	CYP6ER1	.000	.989	560.258	1.000
	CYP6AY1	.000	.980	301.558	1.000
	Carboxyesterase	.000	.905	56.858	1.000
YEAR_	Transposon	.000	.913	62.828	1.000
	Endoglucanase	.039	.537	6.952	.598
	CYP6ER1	.270	.198	1.478	.177
	CYP6AY1	.011	.687	13.162	.854
	Carboxyesterase	.040	.534	6.866	.592
MONTH_	Transposon	.002	.884	45.742	.997
	Endoglucanase	.098	.538	6.994	.434
	CYP6ER1	.030	.688	13.248	.705
	CYP6AY1	.035	.672	12.286	.671
	Carboxyesterase	.224	.392	3.874	.261
YEAR_ * MONTH_	Transposon	.000	.937	88.676	1.000
	Endoglucanase	.339	.302	2.601	.188
	CYP6ER1	.212	.403	4.058	.272
	CYP6AY1	.055	.620	9.802	.571
	Carboxyesterase	.483	.216	1.649	.135
Error	Transposon				
	Endoglucanase				
	CYP6ER1				
	CYP6AY1				
	Carboxyesterase				
Total	Transposon				
	Endoglucanase				
	CYP6ER1				
	CYP6AY1				
	Carboxyesterase				
Corrected Total	Transposon				
	Endoglucanase				
	CYP6ER1				
	CYP6AY1				
	Carboxyesterase				

a. R Squared = .970 (Adjusted R Squared = .946)

b. R Squared = .734 (Adjusted R Squared = .512)

c. R Squared = .758 (Adjusted R Squared = .556)

- d. R Squared = .855 (Adjusted R Squared = .733)
- e. R Squared = .674 (Adjusted R Squared = .402)
- f. Computed using alpha =

Estimated Marginal Means

1. Grand Mean

Dependent Variable	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Transposon	10.308	.615	8.803	11.813
Endoglucanase	34.663	3.398	26.350	42.977
CYP6ER1	34.511	1.458	30.943	38.078
CYP6AY1	28.568	1.645	24.543	32.594
Carboxyesterase	26.424	3.504	17.849	34.999

2. YEAR, not periodic

Dependent Variable	YEAR, not periodic	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Transposon	2017	5.433	.870	3.305	7.562
	2018	15.183	.870	13.055	17.312
Endoglucanase	2017	25.705	4.805	13.948	37.462
	2018	43.622	4.805	31.865	55.379
CYP6ER1	2017	32.738	2.062	27.693	37.784
	2018	36.283	2.062	31.238	41.329
CYP6AY1	2017	34.537	2.327	28.844	40.230
	2018	22.600	2.327	16.907	28.293
Carboxyesterase	2017	17.242	4.956	5.115	29.368
	2018	35.607	4.956	23.480	47.733

3. MONTH, period 12

Dependent Variable	MONTH, period 12	Mean	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Transposon	6	5.375	1.065	2.768	7.982
	8	10.000	1.065	7.393	12.607
	11	15.550	1.065	12.943	18.157
Endoglucanase	6	43.987	5.885	29.588	58.387
	8	37.477	5.885	23.078	51.877
	11	22.525	5.885	8.126	36.924
CYP6ER1	6	27.135	2.525	20.956	33.314
	8	36.997	2.525	30.818	43.177
	11	39.400	2.525	33.221	45.579
CYP6AY1	6	21.945	2.849	14.973	28.917
	8	36.000	2.849	29.028	42.972
	11	27.760	2.849	20.788	34.732
Carboxyesterase	6	32.325	6.070	17.473	47.177
	8	30.200	6.070	15.348	45.052
	11	16.748	6.070	1.896	31.599

4. YEAR, not periodic * MONTH, period 12

Dependent Variable	YEAR, not periodic	MONTH, period 12	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
Transposon	2017	6	4.150	1.507	.464
		8	9.650	1.507	5.964
		11	2.500	1.507	-1.186
	2018	6	6.600	1.507	2.914
		8	10.350	1.507	6.664
		11	28.600	1.507	24.914
Endoglucanase	2017	6	40.065	8.322	19.701
		8	20.900	8.322	.536
		11	16.150	8.322	-4.214
	2018	6	47.910	8.322	27.546
		8	54.055	8.322	33.691
		11	28.900	8.322	8.536
CYP6ER1	2017	6	22.320	3.571	13.581
		8	39.195	3.571	30.456
		11	36.700	3.571	27.961
	2018	6	31.950	3.571	23.211
		8	34.800	3.571	26.061
		11	42.100	3.571	33.361
CYP6AY1	2017	6	22.600	4.030	12.740
		8	40.310	4.030	30.450
		11	40.700	4.030	30.840
	2018	6	21.290	4.030	11.430
		8	31.690	4.030	21.830
		11	14.820	4.030	4.960

4. YEAR, not periodic * MONTH, period 12

Dependent Variable	YEAR, not periodic	MONTH, period 12	95% Confidence
			Upper Bound
Transposon	2017	6	7.836
		8	13.336
		11	6.186
	2018	6	10.286
		8	14.036
		11	32.286
Endoglucanase	2017	6	60.429
		8	41.264
		11	36.514
	2018	6	68.274
		8	74.419
		11	49.264
CYP6ER1	2017	6	31.059
		8	47.934
		11	45.439
	2018	6	40.689
		8	43.539
		11	50.839
CYP6AY1	2017	6	32.460
		8	50.170
		11	50.560
	2018	6	31.150
		8	41.550
		11	24.680

4. YEAR, not periodic * MONTH, period 12

Dependent Variable	YEAR, not periodic	MONTH, period 12	Mean	Std. Error	95% ...
					Lower Bound
Carboxyesterase	2017	6	22.030	8.584	1.026
		8	27.000	8.584	5.996
		11	2.695	8.584	-18.309
	2018	6	42.620	8.584	21.616
		8	33.400	8.584	12.396
		11	30.800	8.584	9.796

4. YEAR, not periodic * MONTH, period 12

Dependent Variable	YEAR, not periodic	MONTH, period 12	95% Confidence
			Upper Bound
Carboxyesterase	2017	6	43.034
		8	48.004
		11	23.699
	2018	6	63.624
		8	54.404
		11	51.804

Post Hoc Tests

MONTH, period 12

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

Dependent Variable	(I) MONTH, period 12	(J) MONTH, period 12	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
Transposon	6	8	-4.625*	1.5065	.022
		11	-10.175*	1.5065	.001
	8	6	4.625*	1.5065	.022
		11	-5.550*	1.5065	.010
	11	6	10.175*	1.5065	.001
		8	5.550*	1.5065	.010
Endoglucanase	6	8	6.510	8.3222	.464
		11	21.463*	8.3222	.042
	8	6	-6.510	8.3222	.464
		11	14.953	8.3222	.123
	11	6	-21.463*	8.3222	.042
		8	-14.953	8.3222	.123
CYP6ER1	6	8	-9.863*	3.5714	.033
		11	-12.265*	3.5714	.014
	8	6	9.863*	3.5714	.033
		11	-2.402	3.5714	.526
	11	6	12.265*	3.5714	.014
		8	2.402	3.5714	.526
CYP6AY1	6	8	-14.0550*	4.02972	.013
		11	-5.8150	4.02972	.199
	8	6	14.0550*	4.02972	.013
		11	8.2400	4.02972	.087
	11	6	5.8150	4.02972	.199
		8	-8.2400	4.02972	.087
Carboxyesterase	6	8	2.125	8.5838	.813
		11	15.578	8.5838	.119
	8	6	-2.125	8.5838	.813
		11	13.453	8.5838	.168

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

Dependent Variable	(I) MONTH, period 12	(J) MONTH, period 12	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Transposon	6	8	-8.311	-.939
		11	-13.861	-6.489
	8	6	.939	8.311
		11	-9.236	-1.864
	11	6	6.489	13.861
		8	1.864	9.236
Endoglucanase	6	8	-13.854	26.874
		11	1.099	41.826
	8	6	-26.874	13.854
		11	-5.411	35.316
	11	6	-41.826	-1.099
		8	-35.316	5.411
CYP6ER1	6	8	-18.601	-1.124
		11	-21.004	-3.526
	8	6	1.124	18.601
		11	-11.141	6.336
	11	6	3.526	21.004
		8	-6.336	11.141
CYP6AY1	6	8	-23.9154	-4.1946
		11	-15.6754	4.0454
	8	6	4.1946	23.9154
		11	-1.6204	18.1004
	11	6	-4.0454	15.6754
		8	-18.1004	1.6204
Carboxyesterase	6	8	-18.879	23.129
		11	-5.426	36.581
	8	6	-23.129	18.879
		11	-7.551	34.456

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

Dependent Variable	(I) MONTH, period 12	(J) MONTH, period 12	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
	11	6	-15.578	8.5838	.119
		8	-13.453	8.5838	.168

Multiple Comparisons

LSD

Dependent Variable	(I) MONTH, period 12	(J) MONTH, period 12	95% Confidence Interval	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
	11	6	-36.581	5.426
		8	-34.456	7.551

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square(Error) = 147.363.

*. The mean difference is significant at the